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8 1. Traditional approaches to identification of therapeutic targets in cancer have included use of
9 genetically engineered animal models and in vitro cell culture systems for discovery and validation.

10 2. Figure 1: In vitro cell culture cancer models are useful tools for general study of cancer whose use
11 in systems biologic discovery for target discovery is error-prone.

12 a. NES, encoding nestin, in human melanoma cells in vitro.

13 i. Nestin is differentially expressed and silenced in melanoma cells in vitro.

14 b. NES, encoding nestin, in primary tumors of humans with melanoma.

15 i. Nestin is activated in the primary tumor in vivo in humans with melanoma.

16 3. Nestin is a molecule whose expression now appears central to cancer cell biology pertinent to the
17 processes of invasion and migration, in general but also particularly in certain types of cancers with more
18 aggressive tendencies like triple negative breast cancer and malignant melanoma.

19 4. Based on study of tissue gene expression in the solid tumor itself, nestin silencing can be
20 assumed to be false: an in vitro artifact attributable to mode of experimentation.

21 5. The centrality of nestin in a cancer gene expression program and the specific importance of
22 nestin-associated functions in cancer cell behavior is intended to be a representative rather than
23 argumentative situational description in cancer discovery.

24 6. Concept: only study of gene expression in the primary tumor in humans with cancer in vivo
25 (measured using the actual solid tumor ex vivo) can be trusted to provide fully accurate information
26 regarding identity of therapeutic targets based on their up-regulation in the tumor.

27 7. Metastasis is the major proximal cause of death in humans with cancer.

28 8. Approximately 1.95 million new cases of cancer are diagnosed in the United States each year.

9. Approximately 20 million new cases of cancer are diagnosed each year world-wide.

10. Approximately 300,000 new cases of breast cancer are diagnosed in the United States each year.

11. Approximately 2.3 million new cases of breast cancer are diagnosed each year world-wide.

12. Breast cancer is now commonly referred to as “invasive breast cancer”, or IBC, due to frequency
13 of dissemination (as compared to local disease in the breast) in the human population.

14. The first step in metastasis or disease progression in humans with breast cancer is known as
15 regional metastasis, where disease spreads to the lymph nodes: lymph node metastasis.

16. Lymph node metastasis is a precursor to and/or requisite event for metastasis to distant sites.

17. 5-year overall survival for humans with stage I (local) breast cancer is above 90%. Less than 10%
18 of these patients will expire within 5 years.

1 16. 5-year overall survival for humans with stage IV breast cancer, metastatic breast cancer which has
2 spread to a distant organ site, is approximately 25%. Nearly 75% of these patients will expire within 5
3 years.

4 17. Metastasis to the lymph nodes precedes and predicts a difficult to manage type of metastasis,
5 metastasis to the central nervous system (CNS).

6 18. Aim: We will perform drug discovery for metastasis to the lymph node using blind, systematic
7 identification of therapeutic targets using primary tumor and lymph node metastasis transcriptome data to
8 precisely calculate lymph node metastasis-specific vulnerabilities.

9 19. Aim: We will discern functional significance or biologic relevance of these (the therapeutic
10 potential associated with blocking the target) using human survival data from a large cohort of humans
11 with breast cancer.

- 12 a. These data can also provide important information regarding biologic intent associated with up- or
13 down-regulation of the gene (molecule) in question.
- 14 b. Because the gene was identified in the actual human system for which the therapeutic is being
15 designed, and the human survival data (the longitudinal quality and depth ($n=2765$)) is of sufficient
16 capacity, conclusions drawn regarding functional relevance of the transcriptomically identified
17 target are, in general, more likely to be accurate than if assessed in an in vitro system or animal
18 model of cancer.

19 20. Hypothesis: targeting discrete modules with immunoglobulin-based monoclonal antibody reagents
20 designed using tumor transcriptome data in lymph node positive patients will significantly reduce
21 frequency of metastasis to the CNS, blocking disease progression through lymph node metastasis
22 targeting.

23 21. Hypothesis: targeting discrete modules with immunoglobulin-based monoclonal antibody reagents
24 designed using tumor transcriptome data in lymph node negative patients at predicated to be at high-risk
25 of progression to lymph node positive disease will significantly reduce the fraction of patients whose
26 disease progresses using TNM staging within 5 years.

27 22. Compassionate Use, also known as Expanded Access, provides access to an investigational
28 therapeutic (drug) when a life threatening condition exists and no comparable medication is available for
treatment.

29 23. The major requirements for Compassionate Use are:

- 30 a. The patient or patients has/have a life-threatening disease or medical condition.
- 31 b. There is no comparable or satisfactory alternative therapy
- 32 c. The potential benefit outweighs the potential risks
- 33 d. The use does not interfere with initiation, conduct or completion of clinical investigations.

34 24. It is estimated that on average 99% of Expanded Access (Compassionate Use) are approved by
35 the FDA (Food and Drug Administration).

36 25. We used primary tumor and metastasis tissue from independent patient cohorts to define the
37 lymph node metastatic transcriptome in humans.

38 26. The transcriptome-wide analysis encompassed identification of individual gene targets through
39 measurement of total transcription using microarray. We used the primary tumor rather than normal breast
40 as a reference transcriptome to specifically identify genes activated for lymph node metastasis.

41 27. We integrated findings from separate measurements of total transcription to produce a composite
42 list of therapeutic targets in lymph node metastasis in humans.

28. Human survival: specifically distant metastasis-free survival in $n=2765$ was measured and the tumor expression of each gene in the transcriptome was measured, patients were binned into high and low expressing groups, and time to metastasis to a distant organ site, measured over the course of greater than 250 months, was analyzed as a function of tumor expression of the target.

29. Figure 2: A chemokine gradient that promotes metastasis to the lymph nodes.

30. CCR7 expression correlates with metastasis to a distant organ site.

31. CCL24 expression correlates with metastasis to a distant organ site.

32. Figure 3: CD40-CD40LG interactions promote metastasis to the lymph nodes.

33. Figure 4: Natural killer cells are important in lymph node metastasis (cont'd on page 5).

- i. CD180
- ii. CD244

34. **Figure 4:** Natural killer cells are important in lymph node metastasis.

- i. CD180
- ii. CD244

Lymph Node Negative

Lymph Node Positive

Closing Argument

35. Only study of gene expression in the primary tumor in humans with cancer *in vivo* (measured using the actual solid tumor *ex vivo*) can be trusted to provide fully accurate information regarding identity of therapeutic targets based on their up-regulation in the tumor.

- a. Metastasis is the major proximal cause of death in humans with cancer.
- b. The first step in metastasis or disease progression in humans with breast cancer is known as regional metastasis, where disease spreads to the lymph nodes: lymph node metastasis.
- c. Lymph node metastasis is a precursor to and/or requisite event for metastasis to distant sites.
- d. 5-year overall survival for humans with stage I (local) breast cancer is above 90%. Less than 10% of these patients will expire within 5 years.
- e. We performed drug discovery for metastasis to the lymph node using blind, systematic identification of therapeutic targets using primary tumor and lymph node metastasis transcriptome data to precisely calculate lymph node metastasis-specific vulnerabilities.
- f. We discerned functional significance or biologic relevance of these (the therapeutic potential associated with blocking the target) using human survival data from a large cohort of humans with breast cancer.
- g. The basic, translational, pre-clinical and clinical data presented here and elsewhere provide sufficient evidence for study of precision therapeutic targeting in man using transcriptome design-based monoclonal antibody reagents through Compassionate Use subsequent to approval by FDA.

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h. Terms related to biosimilarity and GMP status of a novel monoclonal antibody reagents targeting a gene product apply here.

i. It is estimated that on average 99% of Expanded Access (Compassionate Use) are approved by the FDA (Food and Drug Administration).

Citations